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The powers of audit and risk committees in constraining earnings management

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effects of audit committee and risk committee on earnings management of 13 listed banks in Nigeria, over a period of five (5) years (2017-2021). Audit committee is proxied by audit committee size, while risk committee is proxied by risk committee size. However, earnings management is proxied by Beneish-M Score. Generalized Method of Moments is used to run the panel regression in order to overcome both within and between differences of endogeneity. The results show that audit committee has a negative and significant effect on earnings management. In the same vein, risk committee shows negative and significant effect on earnings management. Overall, both audit and risk committees are determinants of earnings management in banks in Nigeria. Furthermore, the results provide evidence that audit committee and risk committee play important roles in constraining earnings management in Nigeria. These results have implications for regulators, market participants, lenders, shareholders, scholars, policy-makers, and other stakeholders. The study is limited by the number of observations. It is expected that further research would increase the number of observations by adding to the research period or using samples from non-banking sectors. Our results show that the R^2 is xx%. Further research is expected to add other variables that may influence earnings management activities.

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Audit committee size, Beneish-M Score, earnings management, Nigeria, risk committee size.

Introduction

In the past two decades, empirical studies and concerns on earnings management have grown noticeably (Bouaziz et al., 2020; Gulzar, 2011; Ibrahim et al., 2019; Itopa et al., 2022; Jegede et al., 2018; McNichols, 2000; Palacios-Manzano et al., 2021; Shuto, 2007; Sun & Rath, 2008; Tang & Firth, 2011; Vander-Bauwhede & Willekens, 2003; Yahaya, 2015; Yahaya, 2022; Yahaya & Abdulfatah, 2022). Despite the increasing attention from various scholars, it is still contestable the degree to which corporations could reduce earnings management in an attempt to serve shareholders' interest. This has generated more inconclusive findings, thereby leading to more research studies.

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These studies have confirmed that management engages in earnings manipulation for different reasons. Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine the effects of audit and risk committees on earnings management by banks in Nigeria. A review of several empirical studies from continents in the world shows different results. Furthermore, the review also reveals the following research gap; most past studies were done outside Nigeria, all the studies in Nigeria ignore banks. These past studies also completely ignore the roles of both audit and risk committees, which play key roles in reducing the level of earnings management in corporations.

For example, Abdul-Rahman and Ali (2006) investigate the extent of the effectiveness of monitoring functions of audit committee in reducing earnings management among 97 firms listed on the Main Board of Bursa Malaysia over the period 2002-2003. The study reveals that earnings management is insignificant with audit committee. Piot and Janin (2007) investigate the effect of audit committee existence and independence on earnings management in France. The main finding is that the presence of an audit committee existence curbs upward earnings management.

Also, Salleh and Haat (2014) examine the effectiveness of audit committee in constraining earnings management among listed firms on Bursa Malaysia. Specifically, the study explores how audit committee impacts earnings management. The sample for this study consists of 280 companies listed on Bursa Malaysia in 2005-2009. The audit committee characteristics include size, independence, expertise, frequency of meetings and activity disclosure. The discretionary accrual was estimated using the Modified Jones Model (1995) which was used to proxy for earnings management. After controlling for firm size, board size and leverage, the study finds that audit committee size and audit committee meetings at least twice a year shows a significant association with earnings management. Sun et al. (2014) investigate the effectiveness of independent audit committees in constraining real earnings management in US. It is found that audit committee members' additional directorships are positively associated with real earnings management measured by abnormal cash flows from operations, abnormal discretionary expenses and abnormal production costs, suggesting that audit committees with high additional directorships are less effective in constraining real earnings management. Amar (2014) examines the relationship between independence audit committee and earnings management using a sample consisting of 279 firm-year observations concerning the years ranging from 2002 to 2005. The results show that audit committee independence is linked to earnings management.

Inaam and Khamoussi (2016) investigate the influence of audit committee effectiveness on reducing the extent of earnings management, using the results 58 prior studies. The independence of the audit committee, its size, expertise and the number of meetings have negative relationships with earnings management. Susanto (2016) collects empirical evidence about the effects of audit committees' characteristics on earnings management of 62 manufacturing firms which listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2009 until 2012. Characteristics of the audit committee include tenure, gender, education, work experience in accounting and meetings. The results of the research show that gender and education of audit committee, and audit committees' meetings have influences on earnings management. While tenure and financial working experience of audit committee have no influence on earnings management.

Amin et al. (2018) examine the effects of board characteristics on earnings quality moderated by audit quality on companies with concentrated ownership. Board, in this study, referred to an audit committee that assists the board of commissioners to monitor the earnings report. Moderated regression analysis was used in this study to examine the impact of ownership concentration on the earnings quality monitoring model. The examination was conducted on sub-samples based on the level of ownership

concentrations. The study finds four characteristics of the audit committee that influence the earnings quality (independence, expertise and size has positive effects; the other one, meeting, shows negative effect on earnings quality. Furthermore, Toumeh et al. (2020) examine the effect of audit committee independent on earnings management in Jordan. The result shows that audit committee independence is significant.

This study, therefore, seeks to address these research problems by firstly ensuring variables like audit committee size and risk committee size are included in our study. Secondly, this paper ensures that almost all the banks in Nigeria are included. Thirdly, the study uses a panel regression approach with period and cross section effect captured unlike previous studies that used mostly OLS regression which does not capture the heterogeneity effects of firms from different sectors and period. Lastly, the study to the best of our knowledge is the first in the context of Nigeria banking sector to use most recent data, including the period of 2017 and 2021 to investigate the relationship between audit and risk committees' size and earnings management.

This paper is significant to several stakeholders: regulators, shareholders, lenders (creditors), mainstream governments, customers, societies, suppliers, employees and managers. Furthermore, the results are useful in terms of performance improvement, policy formulation, board of knowledge and future research. The remaining part of this paper is divided into four sections. Section two covers theoretical literature, conceptual literature, and empirical literature. Section three covers the research design, population, sample, model specification, data collection methods, data analyses techniques and a priori expectations. Section four covers descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and regression analysis. Finally, section five covers conclusions and recommendations.

Theory and empirical literature

Agency theory offers insights into the management behaviour of corporations since by and large, the nexus between corporate owners (principals) and management (agents) is incentive-based, that is, authority delegation and decentralisation. This primarily involves the relation between the aforementioned two parties. Agency theory is rooted in one of the oldest problems of corporate relationships, that of understanding the relation between the 'master' who is given socially legitimate control over certain actions and the 'servant' who controls the information on which the 'master' acts (Cyert & March, 1992). Berle and Means (1932) introduced the theory to the context of the modern firm where ownership and management is separated. The theory has developed substantially since the 1960s and 1970s (Eisenhardt, 1989) and became centrally concerned with the relationship between two contracting parties. Jensen and Mickling (1976) define an agency relationship as "a contract under which one or more persons, the principal(s) engage other persons (the agents) to perform some service on their behalf which involves delegating some decision-making authority to the agent. The theory assumes that both the principal and the agent are utility maximizers with different interests, and that because of information asymmetry the agent will not always act in the best interests of the principal. The principal can limit the divergence of interest by establishing appropriate incentives for the agent and by incurring costs termed *agency costs* (Jensen & Mickling, 1976).

Agency costs include (1) monitoring expenditure by the principal to limit any aberrant activities of the agent; (2) bonding expenditure by the agent to ensure that the agent would not take certain actions that could harm the principal; and (3) residual loss: the naira equivalent of the reduction in welfare experienced by the principal due to the divergence between the agent's decisions and those decisions which would maximise the welfare of the principal (Jensen & Mickling, 1976). This where the roles of audit and risk committees come into the equation. Their roles are designed to restrict management from

manipulating corporate earnings to their advantages. In the management literature, the principal-agent relation is more or less prototypic of the relation between shareholders (principals) and management (agents). The formation, as Cyert and March (1992) point out, is a classic one of employment contract. The theory addresses the information problems associated with such contracts. The focus of the theory is “on determining the most efficient contract governing the principal-agent relationship given assumptions about people (e.g. self-interest, bounded rationality, risk aversion), organisation (e.g. goal conflict amongst members), and information (e.g. information is a commodity which can be purchased)” (Eisenhardt, 1989). The theory also seeks to identify an incentive system that can motivate and ensure that the agents would act in line with the principal's interest.

Furthermore, based on the agency theory, the analytical framework for this study will be explained by the agency theory. The agency theory is the most widely used theory to explain corporate governance variables, like in the case of this paper. Agency theory is derived from the relationship between the principal and agent, which has evolved since time immemorial. Shareholders who emerge as the principals, have genuine reasons to delegate their duties to managers, who are the agents in this case, however, because of potential clash of interests, agency theory comes into the equation to resolve such conflicts.

The schematic illustration depicted in Figure 1 shows the framework for this study. It illustrates the interaction with the dependent variable (earnings management) and the independent variables (proxied with corporate board committees' characteristics (which include audit committee size and risk committee size) and earnings management (which is proxied by Beneish M-Score). The analytical framework in Figure 1 leads to further articulation of the model specification in section 3.

Figure 1 Analytical Framework
Source: Authors Design (2023)

In terms of board committees, there are various views on the concept. Some authors proxy board committees by audit committee size. In conformity with previous studies that measured audit committee size by the total number of directors in audit committee, this present research employs the number of members on the audit committee as a measure of audit committee size (ACS). Others view it as risk committee size; in this study, consistent with some of the previously aforesaid studies, risk committee size (RCS) was operationalised as the number of board members in risk committee. In conclusion, following the aforementioned, it is clear from previous studies that earnings management could be viewed from the perspective of Beneish M-Score. Beneish M-Score is measured as $-4.84 + 0.92(\text{Sales Debtor Index}) + 0.528(\text{Gross Profit Index}) + 0.404(\text{Other Asset Index}) + 0.892(\text{Sales Growth Index}) + 0.115(\text{Depreciation Index}) - 0.172(\text{Expenses Index}) + 4.679(\text{Total Accrual Index}) - 0.327(\text{Leverage Index})$. Other measures of earnings management, include but not limited to working capital management model, De Angelo score, Jones Discretionary Accrual Score, Modified Jones Discretionary Accrual Score, Kothari Discretionary Accrual Score, Larcker and Richardson Discretionary Accrual Score, Yoon, Kim and Woodruff Discretionary Accrual Score, Dechow and Dichev Discretionary Accrual Score and Rowchowdhury Earnings Management score.

In order to understand the relationship between board committees and earnings management, there have been various studies conducted in and outside Nigeria. Abdul-Rahman and Ali (2006) investigate the extent of the effectiveness of monitoring functions of audit committee in reducing earnings management among 97 firms listed on the Main Board of Bursa Malaysia over the period 2002-2003. The study reveals that earnings management is insignificant with audit committee. Piot and Janin (2007) investigate the effect of audit committee existence and independence on earnings management in France. The main finding is that the presence of an audit committee existence curbs upward earnings management. Furthermore, Ugbede et al. (2013) investigate the likelihood of audit committee existence and size impacts on earnings management of all the listed Nigerian banks and Malaysian commercial banks for year 2007- 2011. For Nigerian banks, the earnings management has a negative mean, which means that the total accrual was negative in the majority of the sample. On the other hand, total accruals have a positive mean for Malaysian sample banks. Consequently, the residual value in the equation was higher for Nigerian banks compared to Malaysian banks, indicating respectively, lower/higher accruals and earnings quality. Overall, both audit committee presence and size were significant.

Also, Salleh and Haat (2014) examine the effectiveness of audit committee in constraining earnings management among listed firms on Bursa Malaysia. Specifically, the study explores how audit committee impacts earnings management. The sample for this study consists of 280 companies listed on Bursa Malaysia in 2005-2009. The audit committee characteristics include size, independence, expertise, frequency of meetings and activity disclosure. The discretionary accrual was estimated using the Modified Jones Model (1995) which was used to proxy for earnings management. After controlling for firm size, board size and leverage, the study finds that audit committee size and audit committee meetings at least twice a year shows a significant association with earnings management. Sun et al. (2014) investigate the effectiveness of independent audit committees in constraining real earnings management in US. It is found that audit committee members' additional directorships are positively associated with real earnings management measured by abnormal cash flows from operations, abnormal discretionary expenses and abnormal production costs, suggesting that audit committees with high additional directorships are less effective in constraining real earnings management. Amar (2014) examines the relationship between independence audit committee and earnings management using a sample consisting of 279 firm-year observations concerning the years ranging from 2002 to 2005. The results show that audit committee independence is linked to earnings management.

Inaam and Khamoussi (2016) investigate the influence of audit committee effectiveness on reducing the extent of earnings management, using the results 58 prior studies. The independence of the audit committee, its size, expertise and the number of meetings have negative relationships with earnings management. Susanto (2016) collects empirical evidence about the effects of audit committees' characteristics on earnings management of 62 manufacturing firms which listed in Indonesia Stock Exchange during 2009 until 2012. Characteristics of the audit committee include tenure, gender, education, work experience in accounting and meetings. The results of the research show that gender and education of audit committee, and audit committees' meetings have influences on earnings management. While tenure and financial working experience of audit committee have no influence on earnings management. Also, Moses et al. (2016) examine the influence of audit committee characteristics on quality of financial reporting (earnings management) in 15 listed Nigerian banks whose stocks are traded in the Nigerian Exchange as at December 31, 2014. The outcomes of the study depict that audit committee size has no significant effect on earnings management.

Amin et al. (2018) examine the effects of board characteristics on earnings quality moderated by audit quality on companies with concentrated ownership. Board, in this study, referred to an audit committee that assists the board of commissioners to monitor the earnings report. Moderated regression analysis was used in this study to examine the impact of ownership concentration on the earnings quality monitoring model. The examination was conducted on sub-samples based on the level of ownership concentrations. The study finds four characteristics of the audit committee that influence the earnings quality (independence, expertise and size has positive effects; the other one, meeting, shows negative effect on earnings quality. furthermore, Toumeh et al. (2020) examine the effect of audit committee independent on earnings management in Jordan. The result shows that audit committee independence is significant. Also, Erin and Bamigboye (2020) develops index from audit committee size and risk committee size to investigate their impacts on earnings management for 50 financial firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for the period of 2013–2017. The findings empirically reveal that most Nigerian financial firms has a significant impact on the reduction of earnings management practices. The null form of this study hypotheses are stated as follows:

H₀₁: Audit committee size has no significant effect on earnings management.

H₀₂: Risk committee size has no significant effect on earnings management.

The remaining sections of this paper are organized into three sections: section three (3), which is on data and methods. Section four (4), which is on results and discussions and section five (5), which is on summary, conclusions and recommendations. Furthermore, the references of the study are appended, after section five.

Data and methods

This section, titled, data and methods, explains the techniques and approach employed in carrying out the empirical study on the extent of earnings management in Nigerian quoted banks. To this end, the section begins with the research design, closely followed by the population of the study. This is followed by the sample size and sampling techniques, before we have a method of data collections which is closely followed by model specification and techniques of data collection and analysis. In this study, the research method adopted was an expo-facto type of research and content analysis and ratios were used as methods of data collection. The study is longitudinal covering a period of five (5) years. That is, from 2017 to 2021 employing banks quoted on the Nigerian Exchange. The population of the study consists of all the fifteen (15) banks quoted on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) as at 31st December, 2021. The financial statements of these quoted firms were statutorily published and made available to the general public. The data was provided by MachameRatios®. Jaiz Bank Plc and Eco Bank Plc were excluded, leaving us with 13 listed deposit money banks for the study.

The sample size for the study were thirteen (13) banks. This chosen sample size for the study is thus, consistent or in line with the suggestion made by Kerjice and Morgan (1970) that a minimum of five percent (5%) of a defined population is considered as being adequate sample size required for generalization. In this present case, the sample size is about 87 percent (13/15). The study uses secondary data (historical data) collected in respect of the variable captured covering the time frame of five years (2017 to 2021). Most previous studies have used annual financial statements. According to Gray et al. (1995), annual financial statements is the main official and legal document produced by companies on a regular basis and an important medium for their communications. Companies exercise control over the annual financial statements to prevent any possible journalistic information distortion or interpretation (Gray et al., 1995).

Also, according to Tilt (2001), financial statements are mandatory by legislation to be regularly produced particularly by all quoted corporate entities and by these facts making comparisons quite easy or simple. In this study, secondary data were used.

Table 1. *Operationalization of variables and expected signs*

Serial	Variables	Notations and Sources	A priori expectations sign
1	Y, Earnings management	EM, measured with Beneish M-Score, which is measured as $-4.84+0.92(\text{Sales Debtor Index})+0.528(\text{Gross Profit Index})+0.404(\text{Other Asset Index})+0.892(\text{Sales Growth Index})+0.115(\text{Depreciation Index})-0.172(\text{Expenses Index})+4.679(\text{Total Accrual Index})-0.327(\text{Leverage Index})$	
2	X ₁ , Audit committee size	ACS, measured as the total directors and non-directors in the audit committee	-
3	X ₂ , Risk committee size	RCS, measured as is the total directors and non-directors in the risk committee	-
4	X ₃ , Leverage	LEV, total liabilities over total assets	+/-
5	X ₄ , Firm size	FS, natural logarithm of total assets	+/-

Source: Authors (2023)

In this study, the model is specified to capture the two (2) board committees (audit committee size and risk committee size) characteristics and the extent of earnings management. Thus, the study adapted the model specified by Erin and Bamgboye (2020) which was modified for the purpose of establishing the relationship between the dependent variable and the linear combinations of independent variables captured in the study. Therefore, the model reflects the identified board committees' characteristics and the extent of earnings management. The model was specified as:

$$EM_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 ACS_{i,t} + \beta_2 RCS_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEV_{i,t} + \beta_4 FS_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

As indicated earlier, EM is earnings management based on Beneish M-Score; ACS is audit committee size, RCS is risk committee size, LEV is leverage and FS is firm size, both are control variables.

Thus, our *a priori* expectations as indicated in Table 1 are stated as follows:

X₁>0: Means that a rise in audit committee size will lead to a decrease in earnings management.

X₂>0: An increase in risk committee size will lead to decrease in earnings management.

The econometric technique adopted in this study is Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) regression technique. The rationale for its usage is based on the following justifications: the data collected have time and cross-sectional attributes that gives room for studying earnings management over time (time series) as well as across the sampled firms (cross-section); panel data regression provides better results since it increases sample size and reduces the problem of degree of freedom (Muhammad & Ali, 2018); it avoids the problem of multicollinearity and help to capture the individual cross-sectional (or firm-specific) effects that the various pools may exhibit with respect to the dependent variable in the model. Hausman and Taylor (1981) also recommended panel data estimation method because it enables a cross-sectional time series analysis which

usually makes provision for a broader set of data points, but also because of its ability to control heterogeneity and endogeneity issues. Hence panel data estimation allows for the control of individual-specific effects usually unobservable which may be correlated with other explanatory variables included in the specification of the relationship between dependent and explanatory variables. In evaluating the panel regression results, the GMM is used to run the regression and test the hypotheses. The individual statistical significance test (T-test) and overall statistical significance test (F-test) are used. Importantly, the goodness of fit of the model is ascertained using the coefficient of determination (R^2). Our panel analysis is done after descriptive statistics and correlation analysis. All analyses are conducted at 5% level of significance using STATA 16 software.

Empirical results

This section, titled, section four (4), discusses the results of our analyses (descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and GMM regression analysis). Table 2 is a report of the descriptive statistics of the variables of interest.

Table 2 *Descriptive Statistics*

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
EM	65	2.637	.999	.73	9.06
ACS	65	5.954	.543	4	7
RCS	65	6.677	2.055	4	12
LEV	65	28.385	15.383	10	53
FS	65	9.204	.715	7.08	10.07

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

From Table 2, moving from left to the right, the dependent variable is EM, which stands for earnings management. Next to it is the number of observations, which is 65 (13 multiplied by 5 years), which applies to all variables used in this study. The next from Table 2 is the arithmetic mean of EM, which is 2.637 (note that the figures are in absolute values). The standard deviation, which, measures the spread of distribution is .999. In addition, it has minimum mean of .73 and maximum mean of 9.06 points. In terms of the independent variables, ACS, which stands for Audit Committee Size has a mean of approximately 6 members, which is in line with the minimum requirements by the Nigerian Corporate Governance Code (NCGC) 2018 of 3 members. It has a standard deviation of 1 member with a minimum mean of 4 members and a maximum mean of 7 members. Similarly, RCS shows a mean of about 7 members, which is more than the minimum requirement of 3 members according to the NCGC. Its spread is 2 members; it also has a minimum of 4 members and a maximum of 12 members. In terms of control variables, LEV, which stands for leverage, has a mean of 28 percent, which is not alarming. It shows a standard deviation of 15 percent, with a minimum mean of 10 percent and a maximum mean of 53 percent (managers of such banks should be concerned). Finally, FS, which stands for firm size, show a mean of 9.204 points, with a standard deviation of .715 points, with a minimum mean of 7.08 and a maximum mean of 10.07 points.

We also carry out a correlation analysis to show the bivariate relationships between the dependent and independent variables and control variables. The results are contained in Table 3 as follows.

Table 3 *Correlation Matrix*

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
(1) EM	1.000				
(2) ACS	-0.010* (0.009)	1.000			
(3) RCS	-0.065* (0.006)	0.337* (0.006)	1.000		
(4) LEV	-0.048 (0.706)	-0.026 (0.838)	0.173 (0.168)	1.000	
(5) FS	-0.197 (0.115)	0.027 (0.831)	0.209 (0.095)	0.338* (0.006)	1.000

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

As shown in Table 3, audit committee size is negatively and significantly correlated with earnings management. In the same vein, risk committee size is negatively and significantly correlated with earnings management. These two results are consistent with our a priori expectation signs. An increase in audit committee size should allow for greater oversight by audit committee members, thereby, discouraging management from earnings manipulation. In the same context, an increase in risk committee members should provide much needed checks or oversights on the activities of the firm that are risky. However, on the two control variables, though, they are negative, none is significant in relation to earnings management.

Discussion of the results

The result on audit committee size is consistent with the works of scholars (Abdul-Rahman & Ali, 2006; Amar, 2014; Amin et al., 2018; Inaam & Khamoussi, 2016; Piot & Janin, 2007; Salleh & Haat, 2014; Sun et al., 2014; Susanto, 2016; Toumeh et al., 2020). Furthermore, the result on risk committee size is consistent with the works of some scholars such as contained in parenthesis (Abdul-Rahman & Ali, 2006; Amar, 2014; Amin et al., 2018; Inaam & Khamoussi, 2016; Piot & Janin, 2007; Salleh & Haat, 2014; Sun et al., 2014; Susanto, 2016; Toumeh et al., 2020). Both the two control variables are not significant.

We further conduct a panel data model regression analysis with GMM, since it overcomes the differences of endogeneity within and between the firms. Table 4 reports the results of the GMM regression analysis. From Table 4, audit committee size (ACS) shows a negative and significant effects on earnings management. These results are consistent with our a priori expectations. At the beginning of the paper, we expect that an increase in the members of audit committee size should provide the much needed hands for audit committee members to ensure that earnings management by managers is constrained. Furthermore, the results in Table 4 show that a rise in the members of audit committee reduces earnings management by 1 percent.

Table 4 *Results of GMM*

EM	Coef.	Robust Std. Err.	z	P>z	[95% Conf.	Interval]
ACS	-.0102531	.0849788	-3.12	0.009	-.1563022	.1768084
RCS	-.0142701	.0386903	-3.37	0.001	-.0901018	.0615616
LEV	.0016304	.005739	0.28	0.776	-.0096178	.0128786
FS	-.2788412	.2199269	-1.27	0.205	-.7098899	.1522076
/b0	5.191249	2.137038	2.43	0.015	1.002732	9.379766

Number of parameters = 5

Number of moments = 5

Initial weight matrix: Unadjusted

Number of obs = 65

GMM weight matrix: Robust

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Furthermore, Table 4 shows that risk committee size (RCS) has a negative and significant effects on earnings management. These results are consistent with our a priori expectations. Just like audit committee size, at the beginning of the paper, we expect that an increase in the members of risk committee size should provide the much needed hands for risk committee members to ensure that earnings management by managers is reduced. Furthermore, the results in Table 4 show that a rise in the members of risk committee reduces earnings management by 1.4 percent. Although, the impacts of these board committees characteristics on earnings management are minima; other corporate governance characteristics such as external corporate governance, ownership structure, external auditors, boards of directors, other board committees, are needed to ensure that earnings management by managers are reduced to its barest minimum. In terms of the two control variables, managements of the sampled banks should not waste time and money on them because the regression results have shown that they do not constrain earnings management.

This study also brings new light on the roles of both audit committee size and risk committee size in reducing earnings management behaviour of managers in a corporate setting, specifically, in banks. Furthermore, this study provided evidence on the monitoring effectiveness of audit committee and risk committee. One key finding is that firm leverage and firm size do not play any role in restricting earnings management. The results also raise a question on how much relevant is gearing and firm size in the body of literature concerning earnings management behaviour of managers.

Summary and conclusions

This article advances the body of knowledge with respect to earnings management literature in the Nigerian banking context by examining the effect of the role of audit and risk committees' size. The results of this current study offer original and beneficial information for the Nigerian stakeholders with a similar institutional environment because the study promotes the application of audit and risk committees' size as efficient tools to constrain management behaviour towards manipulation of corporate earnings. On top of that, this research offers information concerning the prevailing situation of earnings management practices and board committees in Nigeria, in which shareholders, local and international investors, policymakers, regulators and academic researchers are interested. Finally, panel data analyses and various statistical techniques are employed to derive

conclusions.

This study contributes to the learning generally, and with specific respect to the roles of audit committee and risk committee in earnings management literature by providing empirical evidence on their relationships. Furthermore, the study adds to the meagre existing evidence on the roles of audit committee and risk committee of the boards of directors in reducing earnings management by managers.

The study findings are relevant for the practitioners who develop their future research and make decisions on the best ways to examine the research problem and problem solutions. This paper helps them to find and preserve the best practices of corporate governance. The results of the study also provide much needed information for good corporate governance.

Conclusively, the study proceeds by discussing how agency theory helps to resolve the conflict of interests between the principals (owners) and agents (managers) in a corporate setting. The results documented the negative influences of some board committees. By these results, several students would be able to gain access to a body of additional knowledge. The findings also demonstrated that firms' characteristics, such as financial leverage and firm size, which are common control variables are not significant in the context of the roles of both audit committee and risk committee in earnings management. There was considerable benefits derivable from this paper (1) there is room for policy improvement (2) there is room for performance improvement (3) there is room for further research and (4) there is room for additional body of knowledge.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

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